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Elemental considerations about the largest FTA in the world between the EU and Japan

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Abstract

Despite the historical economic and political rivalry, the new free trade agreement (FTA) between the European Union (EU) and Japan was finally signed and entered into force at the beginning of 2019. After more than five years of negotiations, this FTA, currently the largest in the world, represents a relevant example of tariff liberalization. Therefore, this paper seeks to analyze specific characteristics in this unprecedented trade agreement and its parts, which as a full ensemble, accumulate values close to one third of total world imports and exports.

Keywords: Free Trade Agreement, Liberalization, European Union, Japan.

Introduction

Historically, free trade agreements (FTAs), as a tool for liberalization, date from the second half of the nineteenth century, specifically with the Cobden-Chevalier Treaty signed between France and the United Kingdom, which set a unique precedent in the history of international trade. For example, after decades of protectionism in Europe, this agreement became a milestone in trade liberalization as several countries used it as an example for subsequent agreements. In addition, this commercial agreement included the first use of a Most Favoured Nation (MFN) clause, which requires that those states party to an agreement must mutually guarantee to each other the best conditions that each of them grants to any other third state (Lazer, 1999).

In this way, international trade agreements such as FTAs aim to consolidate a free trade zone where member states eliminate customs restrictions, especially tariff barriers relating to reciprocal trade products. This process of liberalization involves a period of transition where, gradually, states tend progressively to eliminate the obstacles to bilateral trade according to the capacities and compatibility of the economies involved. International trade agreements are regulated by the provisions of the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT), with article XXIV and also the enabling clause as part of the Tokyo Round within World Trade Organization (WTO) (Cardona, 2017).

According to Fernandez (2009), the current vicissitudes of the world economy are substantially changing the parameters of social development in all countries that are faced with the challenge that the effects of economic and commercial globalization have on a state's sovereignty and their social policies including the supra-nationality that entails the GATT-WTO paradigm. In fact, the current difficulties within the GATT-WTO paradigm related to political will, consensus and supra-national issues seem to push countries to seek new alternatives to trade liberalization through tariff reductions leaving the role of the international trading system and giving an outstanding protagonist of trade agreements (Cardona, 2015).

Hence the number of FTAs tends to increase globally, as these also create opportunities to ensure the benefits of liberalization that GATT provisions and other legal texts do not provide in certain circumstances. FTAs provide alternatives to other negotiated commitments with other countries so as to promote the commercial exchange of goods and services (Oxley, 2004).

Likewise, EU trade policy is in flux and has shown remarkable development. This is due to the deepening of the global trade liberalization agenda, the EU's constitutional recasting of the Common Commercial Policy, and the politicization of trade. Thus it is clear the EU is focusing on the signing FTAs with new markets such as South Korea, the US, Canada, and Japan and therefore its trade policy focuses on a new approach takes the regulatory turn and sheds light on its ramifications for the mobilization of new actors with the involvement its full member countries (Laursen & Roederer-Rynning, 2017).

In that regard, this article aims to highlights some important facts related with the new FTA currently in place between the EU and Japan, referred to as largest free trade agreement in the world, as well as carry out general analysis about this FTA to draw conclusions.

Background about FTA between the EU and Japan

According to Basedow (2018), the GATT-WTO seems to be in a complicated situation where ministerial conferences and trade negotiations stop moving forward as countries fail to agree on certain essential trade issues as the Doha round has recently shown. Thus, this scenario has shaken the confidence in global governance within the current multilateral trading system and called into question the functionality of this supranational model among all the full members.

It should be noted that within the WTO, there is an essential principle where decisions are always adopted by consensus and nothing is agreed until everything is agreed. However, the lack of political will has led to major consensus failures regarding this initial statement; which opens a debate on a possible crisis in the WTO that would require significant structural changes within the regulatory body (Jones, 2011).

This is an important reason why FTAs take an indisputable role since decisions within the GATT-WTO, and consequently, in the multilateral trading system, are not being achieved in the way expected. Precisely because of this, the FTAs end in parallel allowing the member countries concerned to regulate a multiplicity of specific issues in trade that for political reasons currently take too long within the WTO when the multilateral negotiations are not satisfactorily achieved (Alvstam, Kettunen, & Ström, 2017).

In short, it can be said that the process of liberalization of world trade is in a difficult situation where the current multilateral approach of the GATT-WTO has taken an entirely political tinge that relies on consensus for the closure of the processes of trade negotiations among the full members of the international trading system. Therefore, although the WTO was created to manage world trade, a growing proportion of world trade is also managed through bilateral trade agreements due to these international agreements allowing the creation of rules for the regulation of trade flows of goods and services for all parties involved (Farrands, 2018).

Also, after the Great Recession at the end of the 2000s witnessed a relevant collapse of international trade and many governments around the world were affected. Hence, the economic recession can be understood as one of the phases of the global business cycle because states, in general, had suffered from this enormous crisis episode. Nevertheless, the depth of this phase was different across the countries because of their trade policy approach. Some of the most important economies in the world were affected by the crisis such as the United States, the EU, and Japan, whose governments adopted many strategies related with monetary and fiscal policy to bring about an economic recovery. Furthermore, they planned to use a new FTA to aid their recovery efforts. (Mazurek & Mielcová, 2013; Osińska, Kufel, Błażejowski, & Kufel, 2016).

Therefore, the change of external trade policy both between the EU and Japan created an overarching framework for enhanced political cooperation as well as joint actions on matters of common interest to address regional and global challenges. The EU and Japan are two huge economies, which together account for almost one-third of the world's total GDP and even more than a fifth of world trade (Prats, 2011; Bacon, Mayer, & Nakamura, 2016; European Union, 2018; 2019).

In addition, Christiansen, Defraigne, & Kubo (2018) affirm that the external relations of both Japan and the EU have traditionally been dominated by economic issues. In this way, despite historical differences, their relations have strengthened in recent years considering the background of a global climate that has been growing more hostile to the rise of China and the risks of dependence on this market are currently common concerns for Japan and the EU. Moreover, the recent changes in US foreign trade policy, in particular, withdrawal from transatlantic and trans-pacific trade agreements, have changed the geopolitical scenario. This creates a higher priority for the EU and Japan to cooperate in order to ensure their economic security, both bilaterally, so in this sense, this is a definite proof of convergence between the EU and Japan.

The stated intention of the United Kingdom to withdraw from the European Union in 2019 has required the EU to find trade alternatives to minimize the disruption caused by the withdrawal of the world's ninth biggest economy. This will surely have economic impacts on the Union and increase trade uncertainty for the remaining members. Thus, this complicated political and economic situation represents a fundamental challenge post-Brexit for the EU, and Japan could, as an outstanding market, offer solutions in this regard (Perraton & Spreafico, 2019; Anderson & Wittwer, 2018).

In short, on the one hand, there are historic latent difficulties in achieving multilateral stable integration processes at a regional level in Asia between economic powers such as China and Japan. On the other hand, the historic latent difficulties achieving multilateral stable integration processes at a regional level in Europe between the United Kingdom and the EU have meant a new opportunity for developing new initiatives such as this FTA between economic powers that have had profound political differences as has happened with Japan and the EU (Huang & Reilly, 2018).

The role of FTA for the trade liberalization within the multilateral trading system

Since the end of the Uruguay Round and the creation of the GATT-WTO paradigm with all its full members, the multilateral trading system has been an extraordinary scenario for trade negotiations that aim to contain protectionism which tends to threaten the dynamics and growth of international trade (Baena & Fernández, 2016; Cardona, 2018). Problems such as economic crises usually exert pressure on states which then tend to alter their trade policy so as to increase both tariff and non-tariff barriers. This increases economic uncertainty and entails a slowdown in the world economy (Baena, Montoya, & Torres, 2017).

When difficulties arise in the international economy, trade agreements can emerge as an alternative to the multilateral trading system and liberalize trade between states. In recent years, the effect of FTAs on world trade flows has increased fivefold given that, on average, an FTA doubles the bilateral trade of the member parties in the medium term; therefore, these trade agreements are a key element to reduce protectionism (Baier & Bergstrand, 2007).

In fact, the globalization of the world economy is characterized by the remarkable growth of trade flows in goods, services and foreign investment. Indeed the FTAs are a tool for countries to manage this phenomenon since they allow an increase in access to markets, promote investment, and a way for states to protect themselves from unfair trade measures, among many other options (Lynch, 2010). This is despite protectionism as a trade policy being able to help to protect un-competitiveness within a national market through using both tariff and non-tariff means, in order to reduce foreign trade flows such as imports in the local market (Bernitz & Ringe, 2010).

Hence, signing an FTA creates an easier and relatively quick way to liberalize trade with certain trading partners and negating the negotiation processes within the multilateral trading system where full members do not always reach consensus on specific trade issues as has been happening in the Doha Round within the WTO. Even an FTA is usually a more accessible path concerning the signing of other more ambitious political-economic initiatives, such as, for example, with multilateral agreements such as economic integration (Lindberg & Alvstam, 2012).

Baldwin (2016) adds that the role of the FTAs has reached such a level of importance in international trade; that these currently constitute, for all countries in the multilateral trading system, a quick option to continue creating new provisions which allow for trade liberalization among the full members of the WTO despite the failure of Doha. Since its creation, the WTO has made substantial progress in promoting free trade among governments however recent consensus problems seem to have created a shift to a decentralized process with trade agreements that have sometimes overlapped with the GATT rules.

Evidence shows that the issue of regulation of tariff barriers and excessive levels of customs tariffs that have historically been present in international trade was without a doubt the *raison d'être* for the old rounds of negotiation in the GATT regime and it continues to be a strategic issue within the WTO. It can be said that tariff-level protectionism is currently under control, due to the GATT provisions and the WTO's legal texts, which has led to a situation where many countries have adopted non-tariff barriers, which proportionally tend to be more abundant, diverse and opaque compared to the tariff barriers (Baena, 2018). It is for this reason that FTAs not only tend to be useful for lowering tariff barriers, but they are especially good at reducing non-tariff barriers. Countries that sign agreements of this nature usually reach concrete commitments to circumscribe and avoid the application of trade policies related to the use of non-tariff barriers in general and in addition issues that relate to rules of origin. In this way, this situation also explains the significant proliferation of FTAs in recent years and takes into account some regulatory issues related with non-tariff barriers within the WTO (Hayakawa & Kimura, 2015).

Regarding FTAs it is necessary to add also that these international agreements have a typology related not only with its number of parties but also with its properties, see Figure 1; i.e. FTAs have some unique features compared to other kinds of international trade agreements where countries reach preferential tariffs and even particular rules of origin for trade liberalization within the WTO (WTO, 2019).

Fig. 1: Properties and features of the FTAs

Source: Based on data from Park & Park (2008), Kolb (2008) & Tejedor (2017)

Because of this, FTAs have become a popular instrument for the promotion of trade liberalization within the multilateral trading system without undermining the WTO. Considering that the same GATT provisions included the article XXIV “Territorial Application – Frontier Traffic – Customs Unions & Free Trade Areas” which it was described the conditions and measures relating to the formation of customs unions and free trade areas by Members. Likewise, FTAs were legitimized in the GATT rounds during the Tokyo Round in 1979 when the “Enabling Clause” was created. It then became possible to sign trade agreements between countries in order to reduce or eliminate obstacles in their reciprocal trade whilst taking into account the application of the Principle enshrined in the Article I of the GATT, on Most Favoured Nation Treatment. Therefore, both regulatory provisions allow for the implementation of international agreements, including FTAs, as long as they do not represent a detriment to third-country trade (Kinoshita & Barbosa, 2015).

Regarding FTAs, it should be said that these, as international agreements, began during the second half of the nineteenth century specifically with the Cobden-Chevalier Treaty signed between France and the UK, which set unique precedents in the history of international trade. For example, with this treaty the countries of Europe, after decades of protectionism, ended up being linked in a joint process of trade liberalization through adaptations to this initial treaty. In addition, this agreement was a milestone to the development of the MFN clause, which requires that those countries that ratify an agreement must mutually grant the best conditions that each of them provides to any other country. Thus, this last aspect has led to the current trade agreements usually consider this clause for third parties moreover this same clause it was already contained in the article I "General Most-Favoured-Nation Treatment" of the GATT (Corbin & Perry, 2019).

Methodology

First of all, a theoretical framework and literature review were drawn up from relevant academic papers and books. These were largely found through the use of databases such as Web of Science, Scopus, Science Direct and even Google Scholar.

Then for the purpose of identifying specific characteristics in the EU-Japanese FTA relevant websites belonging to official sources and organizations such as the WTO, the World Bank, the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) were consulted.

The case of the EU-Japan FTA was taken due to it being recently created and its current status as the largest FTA in the world.

In this way, the results of this paper were developed through a qualitative analysis including tables, figures, and graphics which show some important indicators relating to the EU-Japanese FTA which explain possible differences between these markets.

Results and Discussion

With a view to recognizing some specific features of the FTA between the EU and Japan, a case study is conducted with the available data from reliable sources. For instance, in this first part of the results, FTAs are compared to other kinds of international trade agreements to show how prevalent are the FTAs are for trade liberalization as compared to preferential trade arrangements, partial scope agreements and even economic integrations.

Figure 2: Neo-protectionism and conventional protectionism in international trade

Source: Based on data from WTO (2019a)

As shown in Figure 2, most of the international trade agreements are FTAs, i.e. more than two-thirds of these agreements. This can be because nowadays they are the most convenient way to carry out agreements between states compared to PTAs and PSs which have lost relevance. Especially in regard to EIs which often cover economic, politics, trade and social issues that take a long time to address.

Thereby in this second part, the largest FTAs in the world are listed however the EU-Japan deal stands out in relation to the others because of its size.

Table 1: The 20 larger FTAs in the world according to some foreign trade statistics

N	FTA ¹	In force	Exports	%	Imports	%	GDP total	%
1	EU - Japan	2019	6.584.715.633	37,13%	6.452.684.500	36,11%	22.149.834	27,45%
2	South Korea- United States	2012	2.119.696.447	11,95%	2.886.864.311	16,15%	20.921.355	25,93%
3	United States - Australia	2005	1.776.232.286	10,02%	2.636.836.881	14,76%	20.714.025	25,67%
4	United States - Singapore	2004	1.910.241.057	10,77%	2.726.094.084	15,25%	19.714.511	24,43%
5	United States - Colombia	2012	1.583.021.909	8,93%	2.454.410.657	13,73%	19.699.795	24,42%
6	United States - Chile	2004	1.615.298.336	9,11%	2.473.456.875	13,84%	19.667.680	24,38%
7	United States - Peru	2009	1.590.307.028	8,97%	2.448.159.058	13,70%	19.601.993	24,29%
8	United States - Morocco	2006	1.571.423.178	8,86%	2.453.344.372	13,73%	19.499.743	24,17%
9	United States - Panama	2012	1.557.519.079	8,78%	2.428.695.144	13,59%	19.452.442	24,11%
10	EU - Canada	2017	6.307.120.235	35,57%	6.213.931.220	34,77%	18.930.740	23,46%
11	EU - South Korea	2011	6.460.245.813	36,43%	6.259.679.361	35,03%	18.808.448	23,31%
12	EU - Mexico	2000	6.296.069.822	35,51%	6.201.579.307	34,70%	18.427.616	22,84%
13	EU - SADC	2016	6.056.211.973	34,15%	5.945.129.138	33,27%	17.938.454	22,23%
14	EU Colombia, Peru - Ecuador	2013	5.986.931.679	33,76%	5.886.834.554	32,94%	17.901.334	22,19%

¹ The North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA), in force since 1995, has not been taken into account all this due to this is a unique FTA where its nature does not correspond to bilateral agreement considering its current full members Canada, Mexico and United States.

15	EU - Chile	2005	5.955.847.702	33,59%	5.846.271.925	32,71%	17.554.773	21,76%
16	EU - Egypt	2004	5.912.561.691	33,34%	5.847.549.088	32,72%	17.513.066	21,71%
17	EU - Ghana	2016	5.899.522.278	33,27%	5.793.798.690	32,42%	17.325.027	21,47%
18	ASEAN - China	2007	3.565.583.794	20,11%	3.086.960.316	17,27%	14.713.270	18,24%
19	China - South Korea	2015	2.836.961.949	16,00%	2.320.353.166	12,98%	13.768.451	17,06%
20	China - Australia	2015	2.493.497.788	14,06%	2.070.325.735	11,59%	13.561.121	16,81%

Source: Based on data from UNCTAD (2019) & the World Bank (2019)

According to Table 1, the EU- Japan FTA occupies the top position currently because this agreement has reached the highest foreign trade Indicators such exports, imports, and GDP more than any other previous FTA in world trade.

Subsequently, in this third part comparing parts of the current FTA, it is possible to affirm in Table 2 that the EU exports 5.8 billion of dollars to the world and around 306 million of dollars, i.e. 5.20% of its exports to Japan. While Japan exports 698 million of dollars to the world and approximately 90 million of dollars, i.e. 13% of its exports to UE; in this vein may be said, bilaterally, that EU exports are a lot more than Japan tripling the value of this last. However, Japan exports a lot more than the EU in percentage terms.

Table 2: Foreign trade EU and Japan

Bilateral				
Item	Exports	%	Imports	%
UE	306.104.159	5,20%	271.716.879	4,70%
Japan	90.752.635	13,00%	94.006.403	14,00%
World				
Item	Exports	%	Imports	%
EU	5.886.618.444	33,20%	5.781.210.194	32,35%
Japan	698.097.189	3,94%	671.474.306	3,76%
World	17.732.471.048	100%	17.870.731.886	100,00%

Source: Based on data from UNCTAD (2018) and OEC (2018)

In addition, the EU imports 5.7 billion of dollars from the world and around 271 million dollars, i.e. 4.70% of its imports from Japan. Conversely, Japan imports 671 million from the world and approximately 94 million, i.e. 14% of its imports from the EU. It may be said that EU imports about triple the amount that Japan imports from the EU. Then, Japan imports a lot more than the EU in percentage terms and therefore it is evident that Japan is more dependent bilaterally in exports and imports than the EU.

Finally, in this fourth part of the results, it should be noted that trade liberalization between the EU and Japan is significantly different considering that the EU is less restrictive regarding imports and considering the number of international trade agreements signed and moreover all the tariff barriers and non-tariff barriers currently adopted according to their foreign trade policy.

Table 3: Trade liberalization EU versus Japan

Parts Involved	Trade Agreements	Tariff barriers average	Non-Tariff barriers measures
UE	55	1,79	2301
Japan	19	2,51	1740

Source: Based on data from the WTO (2019b) & the World Bank (2019a)

The EU has 55 international trade agreements currently, mostly FTAs, while Japan only has 19 international trade agreements; indeed the EU is the international organization with the most FTAs signed in the world. Likewise, regardless of these agreements, the EU has an average of around 1.79% tariff barriers for all imported products while Japan has an average about 2.51% tariff barriers and almost the same with non- tariff barriers measures, less than six hundred measures apart, for all imported products; thus, it is valid to assume that the level of trade liberalization in Japan is lower than the EU.

Conclusions

The current situation within the WTO with the trade negotiations and all the issues related with global governance in the multilateral trading system, as the Doha round demonstrates, has driven many full members to sign new international trade agreements. Moreover, the FTAs have become the easiest way for trade liberalization and there is an absence of interest in many states for granting preferential and unilateral customs tariffs with PTAs. Then, it is possible to state that troubles in the international trading system are pushing some full members of the WTO to sign new initiatives for trade liberalization even traditional economic and political rivals. All of this is due to the current political will issues of the negotiating rounds within the GATT-WTO paradigm. Similarly, PSs are nowadays quite narrow for addressing some trade matters, that is why FTAs stand out as they allow for negotiating trade issues for goods and services in a wide, friendly and relatively quick manner.

In any case, global governance matters are not the only aspect of acting upon the multilateral trading system. Trade conflicts among some great economic powers generate a new dynamic in the relationships among other great economic power as is the case here.

Last but not least, this new FTA is an outstanding example of how historical differences can be adequately addressed with new trade initiatives within the foreign trade approach between states with the aim of creating development and economic well-being.

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